

Exploratory Study of the Influence of Technology on the Happiness and Well-being of Future Teacher's during Difficult Times of COVID-19

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Teachers are the most crucial human resource and a driving force that immensely contributes to nation-building through education. Teaching learning process in schools is a dynamic process wherein constant changes are experienced in various aspects like pedagogy, learning theories, curriculum, and educational processes, a lot of which provides challenge and comfort to the teachers. Amidst the multi-sectional and dynamic structure of education, teachers' well-being is elicited as one of the concern areas in education. Hence, this study aims to examine the impact of technology on prospective teachers' happiness and well-being in teacher education programmes. The present study is exploratory and qualitative in nature. The data was collected in two phases. In the first phase, the data was collected using two psychological scales to assess the subjective happiness and life satisfaction of Lyubomirsky (2011) and Diener (1985) respectively, along with an online questionnaire which was filled by the respondents. In the second phase of the study, interviews were conducted using a semi-structured interview schedule with the respondents who scored highest and lowest in the results of psychological scales. The sample of the study comprises 48 female prospective teachers studying in a teacher education programme during their fourth-year internship. The respondents were selected through purposive sampling from a teacher education programme enrolled in a college of University of Delhi. The result of the study showed that technology influences prospective teachers' well-being and happiness both positively and negatively in their professional and personal spheres.

Keywords: Prospective teachers, happiness, well-being, technology, teacher education

The central purpose of every human life is to find happiness, and its attainment becomes the very purpose of life (Aristotle as cited in Snyder & Lopez, 2007). Happiness can contribute to one's overall sense of well-being by promoting positive emotions, reducing stress, and enhancing an individual's psychological well-being and physical health (Snyder & Lopez, 2007). Well-being, on the other hand, is a broader concept that encompasses multiple dimensions of our lives, including our physical, psychological, and social health. According to Seligman (2011), PERMA core compo includes: Positive Emotion, Engagement, Relationships, Meaning, and Accomplishments. Well-being is a multidimensional construct that involves a complex interplay of these core components.

Well-being is one of the concern areas which is talked about and has significantly grown in importance post COVID 19. India ranked 136 out of 146 countries, which even makes this arena more sensitive

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and pivotal (United Nations' World Happiness Report, 2022). The individuals' satisfaction with life showed large differences across the world, where India stood lowest in the category.

Teachers play a significant role not only in the teaching-learning process but in shaping the learner's mind. Teachers truly shape the future of the children and, therefore, the future of the nation. It further states that education should develop not only the individuals' cognitive capacities, but also their emotional, social and ethical capacities. Teacher preparation is an activity that requires multidisciplinary perspectives and knowledge, formation of dispositions and values, and development of practice under the best mentors (National Education Policy, 2020). Keeping the view, teacher education can be seen as vital in creating a pool of school-teachers that will shape the next generation. However, it has become a global phenomenon that newly qualified teachers (NQTs) often leave the teaching profession within the first few years after completion of the teacher educational programs (Fantilli & McDougall, 2009). Thus, raising a question on the quality of teacher education being provided is a crucial aspect for the education system.

When it comes to the well-being of prospective teachers, teacher education programmes here as well play a crucial role in the preparation of teachers, especially in the time of pandemic, which has exacerbated the situation (Pressley et al., 2021). The mode of preparation has become more of a blended mode where both online and offline modes are used, both at university level and school level (during the internship practicum of teacher education programme). With this shift, the prospective teachers are expected to have certain basic technological skills for operating in the activities of the teacher education programmes for becoming competent professionals.

Being under the stress of operating such technology related activities and that too being assessed upon, the well-being of these prospective teachers has emerged as an area of concern.

Moreso, the concept of prospective teachers' well-being seems to be missing from the discourse of teachers' education, which prepares prospective teachers for their future role of being a professional teacher.

Objectives of the Study

- To study the subjective well-being and life satisfaction of prospective teachers in a teacher education programme.
- To explore how technology influences prospective teachers' well-being and happiness.

Research Questions

- How does technology influences the happiness and well-being of prospective teachers of the teacher education programme during internship practicum?
- What are the prospective teachers' perceptions and experiences about the use of technology?

Method

Participants

For the research, the researcher has used a purposive sampling type of sampling method.

It refers to a group of non-probability sampling techniques in which units are selected because they have characteristics that are needed in the sample (Best & Kahn, 1995) that is, the research requires prospective teachers from a teacher education programme that were selected "on purpose" in purposive sampling for fulfilling the goal of the research. The sample consists of 48 female prospective teachers enrolled in the final year of an elementary teacher education programme, of four years, affiliated by Central University of Delhi in India.

Research Design

Qualitative research design, an online questionnaire was sent to be filled by the respondents through an online Google Form, having the questionnaire consisting of both open-ended and closed-ended questions. These questions were constructed after reviewing considerable literature in the field. Two psychological tools were administered, the Subjective Happiness Scale and Satisfaction with Life Scale, given by Prof. Sonja Lyubomirsky and Diener. Qualitative analysis was used to analyze the data. Interviews were conducted using a semi-structured interview schedule, constructed by the researcher.

Measure

Interpretation of the scores of the psychological scales

Subjective Happiness Scale (SHS): The results of the Subjective Happiness Scale show that the majority of the respondents, that is, 25 (52%) out of 48 respondents of the study, scored average score, while 19 (40%) out of 48 respondents scored low on SHS. Only 4 (8%) respondents scored high on the scale. The aggregate average scoring of the total sample comes out to be 4.48, which is below the average range of score for college students, that is, 4.5 to 5.5. Finally, it can be inferred from the scores that the total sample of 48 respondents of the study shows an average score that lies low on the Subjective

Happiness Scale.

Satisfaction with Life Scale: The results of the Satisfaction with Life Scale shows that the majority of the respondents of the study scored greater than 20, that is, 30 (63%) out of 48 respondents representing their satisfaction with life. 16 (33%) out of 48 respondents scored less than 20 score representing their dissatisfaction with life and the remaining 2 (4%) respondents who scored equal to 20 score representing their sense of neutrality towards their life's satisfaction or dissatisfaction. A significant percentage, that is, 16 (33%) of the respondents from the total sample showed dissatisfaction at varied intensity.

Data Collection and Analysis

Two psychological scales and sixteen open-ended and closed-ended questions were asked through an online questionnaire via Google Form. The data was analyzed into themes and subthemes, which emerged during the process of data analysis.

Results

Use of Technology by Prospective Teachers

With the use of these technologies in multiple settings, it is crucial to know the satisfaction of the respondents with the usage of technology for this study. All of the 48 (100%) respondents agreed that they use technology in various forms in their lives. Further, the data shows that 40 (83.33%) out of 48 respondents marked their responses as "Yes", indicating their sense of satisfaction with their respective usage of technology. Along with the satisfaction level, devotion of an individual's time is yet another aspect which influences one's satisfaction level. It could be inferred from the data that 35 (72.91%) out of 48 respondents devoted their time to technology for more than or equal to 4 hours during a day. 6 (12.5%) respondents devote more than 8 hours. Since the usage of technology has expanded the horizon that holds access to both our personal and professional lives and further seems to influence it. 20 (41.66%) respondents out of 48 signified that their personal use of technology is greater than their professional, 10 (20.83%) respondents out of 48 stated that their professional usage of technology is greater than the other sphere, 13 (27.08%) respondents claimed their use to be equal in both spheres, and the remaining 5 (10.41%) respondents who couldn't ascertain.

Wide Range of Technology is Being Used

The respondents expressed that they use a wide variety of technology, both hardware and software forms of technology like Mobiles, Laptops, Applications, Sites, and YouTube videos being the most popular forms of technology. Along with the other forms including Study Apps, Professional Websites, Chrome, OTT platforms, and Webtoons, specifically in the professional spheres of their lives.

Determining Well-being during Internship Practicum

The perception of the respondents regarding their understanding of the concept of "well-being" and further determining their own state of being was based on their individual understanding of the concept. The data obtained through online questionnaire reveals that the respondents' view of "well-being" includes few common points of intersections as highlighted, that is, physical, mental, spiritual, emotional dimensions, which shows the synchronization of their

vision of well-being as per Davis (2019) who have identified different types of well-being such as Physical well-being, Emotional well-being, Social well-being, Intellectual well-being, Occupational well-being, Spiritual well-being, and Environmental well-being. It can be inferred from the data that the prospective teachers (respondents of the research) were able to classify different types of states of being under various categories, rather than showcasing an insubstantial understanding of the concept. It was also found that the teacher education programmes facilitate the formation of an accurate sense of the concept of well-being.

For determining their own state of being, responses demonstrating the healthy state of being of the individuals are uncovered by the usage of positive words like “great”, “happy”, “good”, “satisfied”, “calm”, “peaceful”, “better”, etc. Quite a few respondents were able to address the subjectivity of the concept of well-being. Similarly, responses demonstrating the unhealthy state of being of the individuals are uncovered by the usage of specific words like “low”, “stress”, “deteriorated”, “problems”, “pressure”, “impatient”, “Not very good”, “irritated”, etc. The respondents reflected not meeting expectations from themselves, that is, relationship with self, mental and physical stress, inability to manage work and time, and academic pressure.

Technological Effect Perceived by the Prospective Teachers (Positive or Negative)

Out of 48 respondents, 32 (67%) stated that their state of being is affected both positively and negatively, while 12 (25%) responded that their state of being is affected only positively and 4 (7%) responded only negatively through their use of technology. Reasons stated for the positive effect perceived by them consists of accessibility and pool of opportunities, as a mode of stress relief, connecting with people, building new perspective and creativity, and creating awareness of their surroundings, on the other hand, the reasons for the negative effect perceived includes unrealistic expectations arising self-doubt, distraction or waste of time, physical and emotional disadvantages, and negatively affecting their authenticity and originality.

Integration of Technology in Education: During Internship Practicum

Out of 48 respondents, 31 (64.5%) concurred with their integration of technology during the lesson planning process, 15 (32.7%) responded, “to some extent”, and the remaining 2 (3.6%) of the respondents stated “No”. The results indicate that the majority of the respondents were able to integrate technology. Reasons stated by respondents include being able to integrate technology in the lesson planning process, which consists of ideation for activities, going beyond textbooks, easy access to extended literature and text, and cost effectiveness.

For the teaching learning process, 26 (54.16 %) respondents concurred with their integration of technology during the process, 19 (38.9%) respondents stated “No” and the remaining 3 (7.8%) responded “To some extent”. Reasons stated by respondents being able to integrate technology in the teaching learning process encompass classroom management, grabbing learners' attention, and pedagogical innovation. However, inadequate resources and the absence of school infrastructure turned out to be the root cause of the inability of prospective teachers to integrate technology in the specified processes.

Discussion

The research findings establish a relationship among the three variables of the research, that is, prospective teachers, well-being and the influence of technology. It could be inferred that technology has a substantial influence on ascertaining the prospective teachers' well-being. The results of the study are consolidated in the form of a spiral representing prospective teachers' well-being influenced by the use of technology. The arousal and identification of needs to integrate technology decides their motivation to incorporate technology in processes like lesson planning and the teaching learning process during their internship practicum, as a result of the perceived ease of use and usefulness of technology. Based on the entire discourse of the study, the following “*Spiral of prospective teachers' well-being influenced by technology*” demonstrates and summarizes the major findings of this study.

Figure 1

Spiral of Prospective Teachers Well-being Influenced by Technology

As the figure illustrates, with the arousal of the need to integrate technology because of the perceived ease of use and the usefulness of technology, the prospective teachers felt motivated to integrate technology in processes like lesson planning and the teaching learning process during their internship practicum. While integrating the technology in this arena, there are factors, namely infrastructural support and/or teachers' competencies, that influences the satisfaction of the prospective teachers while using technology in the specified processes. The satisfaction level achieved by the prospective teacher generated the emotions that tend to eventually determine their well-being.

Conclusion

Teachers are the nation's builder and one of the professions that hold a crucial role in directly contributing to the building of the foundation of humankind. Prospective teachers, enrolled in the teacher education programmes, are the starting block of becoming professional competent teachers, thus making it clear that their well-being is imperative for the profession. More so, technology has more commonly been identified in the past as having a negative influence on teachers and their well-being. Whilst examples of such negative influence clearly exist. This study took this exploration further and examined the different effects perceived by prospective teachers regarding the integration of technology. It is also important to identify where positive influences on prospective teachers' well-being may be arising, to support prospective teachers more effectively in the future in terms of their needs, in times when demands on their time and on their expertise do not seem to be

diminishing. The onus can be given to the prospective teachers to understand much more exactly when, how, and why their positive well-being can be supported through effective uses of technology to enhance their own learning abilities and the enhancement of the learners' outcomes in their classrooms.

Implications of the Study

The teacher education programmes should create awareness and equip competencies among prospective teachers about the effective usage of technology and its integration in the pedagogical practices in order to improve their teaching strategies and cater to individual needs of learners in a better way and also contribute to their state of well-being positively. Also, the correlation between learning and happiness supports the idea that teaching happiness skills in teacher education programmes can boost the idea of building competent teachers who contribute to raising a society with a healthy state of being, which seems to be the ultimate goal of education.

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